

FACULTY OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION STUDIES
 UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
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REPORT OF ORAL PRESENTATION AND DEFENSE

Title of Research Spiritual Communication for Social Transformation: Prayer Warriors' Intercession as Communicative Acts in Building the Parachurch Culture and Identity for National Development

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Degree program: Doctor of Communication

Date, time, and place of final oral presentation¹ 22 March 2023, 2-4 PM; DComm Zoom Meeting Room

Committee

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Others present²:

Committee' Decision:

Approved Disapproved

Classification:

Invention (I) Publication (P) Confidential (C) Free (F)

Additional remarks or recommendations³:

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¹To be filled out by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies ²To be filled out by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies ³May also be written directly on the copy of the manuscript or in extra sheets